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Research Article

A STUDY ON ANTI HYPERTENSIVE PRESCRIBING PATTERNS AND BLOOD PRESSURE MANAGEMENT IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE

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Abstract:

INTRODUCTION: Systemic arterial hypertension also referred to as hypertension is characterized by persistently high blood pressure (BP) in the systemic arteries. BP is commonly expressed as the ratio of the systolic BP that is, the pressure that the blood exerts on the arterial walls when the heart contracts and the diastolic BP the pressure when the heart relaxes usual limit is 120/80mmHg. Hypertension is widely prevalent in India with large regional variation, greater prevalence in urban areas treatment and control status are low. Hypertension was more in men than women. Hypertension is more common in developed countries, urban population and better socio-economic status individuals. The introduction of a formal definition for CKD has enabled standardize current medical communication facilitate appropriate population. Encourage timely prevention and treatment of kidney disease through screening. The GFR is considered the most reliable indicator of overall kidney function. GFR level below 60 mL / minute / 1.73 m² represents loss of one half or more of the adult level of normal kidney function. Normal GFR varies according to patient age, sex, and body size. The MDRD formula is a better estimate of GFR than those derived from 24-hr urine clearance or the Cockcroft- Gault formula. The abbreviated MDRD formula requires gender, race, and serum creatinine.

AIM: The study aims to mainly Aim to assess the selection of Antihypertensive Drugs in single and combination therapy in patients with chronic kidney disease.

OBJECTIVE: The main objective is to study the prescription patterns of Antihypertensive drugs in patients with chronic kidney disease.

METHODOLOGY: This study is a prospective observational study and the subjects involved in the study are Inpatients in Nephrology department at Government general Hospital, Kurnool. The subjects are selected on the basis of the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION: This study involved 120 CKD patients with hypertension to assess the prescription pattern of anti-hypertensive drugs. In our study, 58% males and 42% females were taken. In the present study most of the patients were given dual therapy (43%) followed by triple therapy (33%), this result is supported with the study by Ashok Kumar malapani et.al., that portrayed dual therapy in (78%) of prescription. Individuals with resistant hypertension will require more than or equal to three drugs out of which one is diuretic. Patients must be approached in a step wise manner beginning with traditional anti-hypertensive therapy followed by additional agents to reach a triple or quadruple or five drug compound regimens. Resistant hypertension is defined as blood pressure that remains above 140/90 mm Hg despite optimal use of three anti-hypertensive medications of different classes, including a diuretic. In the present study diuretics and calcium channel blockers are most preferred class of drugs that is used 31% each, which is supported with the study by Alwin P Saju et.al. Among monotherapy calcium channel blockers were most prescribed drug. In dual therapy Calcium channel blockers and Diuretics, in triple therapy diuretics, Calcium channel blockers, Beta blockers and in multiple therapy Diuretics, Beta blockers, Calcium channel blockers, Central sympatholytics are more frequently prescribed. Among Diuretics, furosemide is the most preferred drug, in Angiotensin receptor blockers, telmisartan. In Beta - blockers, metoprolol, in Alpha and Beta blockers, Labetalol, in Central sympatholytic, Clonidine and in Calcium channel blockers amlodipine /b nifedipine and cilnidipine are more frequently prescribed.

CONCLUSION: Our study concludes that males are more prone to Chronic kidney disease, Based on Age wise distribution 41-50 years, 51-60 years patients were hospitalized more frequently. Most of the patients were prescribed with Dual Therapy and Triple Therapy as most of the patients develops Resistant Hypertension. In Mono Therapy, Calcium channel blockers were more prescribed. Among all Anti-Hypertensives, Calcium channel blockers and Diuretics are most prescribed.

KEYWORDS: Resistant hypertension, Chronic Kidney Disease, Modification of diet in Renal Disease (MDRD), Glomerular Filtration Rate.

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1. INTRODUCTION:

Systemic arterial hypertension also referred to as hypertension is characterized by persistently high blood pressure (BP) in the systemic arteries. BP is commonly expressed as the ratio of the systolic BP that is, the pressure that the blood exerts on the arterial walls when the heart contracts and the diastolic BP the pressure when the heart relaxes usual limit is 120/80mmHg. Hypertension is widely prevalent in India with large regional variation, greater prevalence in urban areas treatment and control status are low. Hypertension was more in men than women. Hypertension is more common in developed countries, urban population and better socio- economic status individuals. About 33% urban and 25% rural Indians are hypertensive.

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is defined by reduction in glomerular filtration rate (GFR) with or without urinary abnormalities of renal duct. The etiologies of CKD are Diabetes mellitus, Interstitial disease, Glomerular disease, Hypertension, Systemic inflammatory disease, Renovascular disease, Congenital and inherited disorders. Since Diabetes and Hypertension is major risk factors for deterioration of renal function which ultimately leads to chronic kidney failure if left untreated. The major risk factors for hypertension includes such as obesity, Excess salt intake, mental stress, smoking and alcohol consumption, inadequate physical activity.

The pathophysiology of hypertension is an area which explain mechanistically the causes of hypertension. Hypertension can be classified by cause as either Essential or Secondary. About 90%-95% of hypertension is essential hypertension. Some authorities define essential hypertension as that which has no known explanation, while others define its cause as being due to overconsumption of sodium and under consumption of potassium. Secondary hypertension indicates that the hypertension is a result of specific underlying condition with a well-known mechanism, such as chronic kidney disease, narrowing

of the Aorta or kidney arteries, or endocrine disorders such as excess Aldosterone, Cortisol, or Catecholamines. Persistent hypertension is a major risk factor for hypertensive heart disease, coronary artery disease, stroke, aortic aneurysm, peripheral artery disease, and chronic kidney disease. The major pathological mechanisms involved in hypertension includes Renin-Angiotensin-Aldosterone System (RAAS), Sympathetic Nervous System Activation, Endothelial Dysfunction, Inflammatory Processes, Genetic Factors, Insulin Resistance and Obesity, Kidney Dysfunction, Age and Lifestyle Factors. The pathophysiology of CKD involves a series of complex and interrelated processes that result in structural and functional changes within the kidneys. Here is an overview of the key pathophysiological mechanisms involved in CKD are Glomerular Damage, Tubulointerstitial Fibrosis, Vascular Changes, Inflammation and Oxidative Stress, Proteinuria, Alterations in Renal Hemodynamics, Activation of the Renin-Angiotensin-Aldosterone System (RAAS), Podocyte Injury, Metabolic and Endocrine Disturbances. The signs and symptoms of CKD includes Elevated serum electrolytes, Proteinuria, Albuminuria (foamy urine), Hematuria

Electrolyte imbalance. The diagnosis of CKD includes measuring Serum creatinine and urea levels in blood Complete urine evaluation, Renal biopsy, Measuring GFR, Albumin, Renal ultrasound Chest x-ray USG abdomen

Protein-creatinine ratio (PCR), Liver function test Renal function test. GFR less than 60 ml/min/1.73m² for greater than equal to 3 months with or without kidney damage. The GFR is considered the best measure of overall kidney function. A GFR level below 60ml/min/1.73m² represents the loss of one half or more of the adult level of normal kidney function. Normal GFR varies according to patients age, sex and body size. The MDRD formula is a better estimate of GFR than those derived from 24 hours urine clearance or the Cockcroft-Gault formula. Diagnosis of chronic

kidney disease traditionally is based on pathology and etiology, broadly divided into diabetic, glomerular, vascular, tubular interstitial and cystic kidney disease. Hypertension is both a cause and complication of CKD and should be carefully controlled in all patients. The Treatment of co-morbid conditions, interventions to slow progression of kidney disease, and measures to reduce the risk for CVD should begin during stage-1 and stage-2. Evaluation and treatment of other complications to slow progression of decreased GFR such as Anemia, Malnutrition Bone disease, Neuropathy and decreased quality of life, should be under taken during stage-3, as the prevalence of these complications begins to rise when GFR declines to less than 60 ml/min/1.73m².

2. AIM & OBJECTIVE

AIM

The study aims to mainly Aim to assess the selection of Antihypertensive Drugs in single and combination therapy in patients with chronic kidney disease.

OBJECTIVE

The main objective is to study the prescription patterns of Antihypertensive drugs in patients with chronic kidney disease.

3. METHODOLOGY:

This study is a prospective observational study and the subjects involved in the study are Inpatients in Nephrology department at Government general Hospital, Kurnool. The subjects are selected on the basis of the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Study Site: Nephrology Department, GGH, Kurnool.

Study Duration: The study was conducted for 6 months.

Study Design: Prospective observational study.

Sample Size: A total of 120 patients.

Study Material: Patient data collection proforma.

INCLUSION CRITERIA

1. Patients diagnosed with CKD and Hypertension.
2. Patients of age whose age is above 18 years are included in our study.
3. Either gender is considered.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

1. Patients whose age is below 18 years are excluded from the study.
2. Pregnant and lactating women are excluded in the study.

DATA COLLECTION:

All the data of the subjects are collected by using the case proforma. The data collection includes the demographic details, past medical history, personal habits, physical examination, blood pressure before and after Antihypertension treatment, laboratory investigations, diagnosis, drug chart.

4. RESULTS

4.1 GENDER WISE DISTRIBUTION OF TOTAL STUDY POPULATION

In our study, among 120 subjects we have observed males are more prone for CKD 58% males and 42% females.

TABLE 4.1 GENDER WISE DISTRIBUTION OF TOTAL STUDY POPULATION

GENDER	NUMBER OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE
MALES	70	58%
FRMALES	50	42%

FIG 4.1 GENDER WISE DISTRIBUTION OF TOTAL STUDY POPULATION

4.2 AGE WISE DISTRIBUTION

Here we have distributed subjects with 10yr difference and observed at which age group subjects has become victims of CKD. As we know that CKD affects more naturally among aged people.

TABLE 4.2 AGE WISE DISTRIBUTION

AGE WISE DISTRIBUTION	NUMBER OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE
21-30 years	8	8.70%
31-40 years	16	16.13%
41-50 years	30	30.80%
61-70 years	38	38.32%

FIG 4.2 AGE WISE DISTRIBUTION

4.3 ANTI HYPERTENSIVES PRESCRIBED IN CKD PATIENTS

All the anti-hypertensives used in CKD are as in the below table among them Diuretics are mostly prescribed as CKD patients comes with the complaints of oliguria, shortness of breath, oedema, because due decreased renal function cannot excrete enough water which leads to hypertension, serum creatinine, blood urea build up.

TABLE 4.3: ANTI HYPERTENSIVES PRESCRIBED IN CKD PATIENTS

CLASS OF ANTIHYPERTENSIVES PRESCRIBED	NUMBER OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE
Diuretics	89	31%
ARBs Blockers	20	7%
ACE Inhibitors	0	0%
CCB	88	31%
Beta blockers	45	16%
Alpha blockers	7	2%
Alpha + Beta blockers	13	5%
vasodilators	3	1%
Nitrates	2	1%

FIG 4.3 ANTI HYPERTENSIVES PRESCRIBED IN CKD PATIENTS

4.4 DIURETICS PRESCRIBED IN CKD PATIENTS

Among 120 patients, diuretics were prescribed to 89 patients. Diuretics are medications that promote diuresis, which is the increased production of urine, commonly used to treat hypertension, heart failure and edema. Among diuretics only Furoseamide is prescribed.

TABLE 4.4 DIURETICS PRESCRIBED IN CKD PATIENTS

DIURETICS PRESCRIBED	NUMBER OF PATIENTS
Diuretics	89
Others	31

FIG 4.4 DIURETICS PRESCRIBED IN CKD PATIENTS

4.5 ANGIOTENSIN RECEPTOR BLOCKERS PRESCRIBED IN CKD PATIENTS

Among all ARB only Telmisartan was prescribed for 20 patients among 120 patients. Angiotensin receptor blockers (ARBs) are a class of medications commonly used to treat conditions such as hypertension, heart failure and chronic kidney disease. TELMISARTAN is an angiotensin –II receptor (ARB), specially blocking the angiotensin-II type I(AT1) receptors. Angiotensin-II is a hormone that plays a key role in the renin- angiotensin –aldosterone system (RAAS), which regulates blood pressure and fluid balance. By blocking the AT1 receptors, telmisartan prevents the action of angiotensin, leading to vasodilation (widening of blood vessels) and reduction in aldosterone release.

4.6 CALCIUM CHANNEL BLOCKERS

calcium channel blocker (CCBs) is a class of medications that primarily target calcium channels in various tissues, including cardiac smooth muscles. Among 120 patients Amlodipine which is a calcium channel blocker (CCBs) were prescribed to 80% of subjects followed by Nifedipine 12% and cilnidipine 8% were commonly prescribed.

TABLE 4.6 CALCIUM CHANNEL BLOCKERS

CALCIUM CHANNEL BLOCKERS	NUMBER OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE
Nifedipine	11	12%
Amlodipine	70	80%
cilnidipine	7	8%

FIG 4.6 CALCIUM CHANNEL BLOCKERS

4.7 OTHERS ANTI HYPERTENSIVES PRESCRIBED

4.7.A. BETA BLOCKER:

Among 120 patients 45 patients have been prescribed beta blockers among beta blockers only metoprolol has been prescribed

4.7.B. ALPHA + BETA BLOCKERS:

Among 120 patients labetalol has been prescribed to 13 patients

4.7.C. CENTRAL SYMPATHOLYTICS:

Among 120 patients only 18 patients have been prescribed with clonidine which is a central sympatholytic. Central sympatholytic are a class of medications that acts within the central nervous system to reduce sympathetic nervous system activity.

4.8 TYPES OF THERAPIES

As CKD stage advances more than one class of anti-hypertensives are used for mortality below graph shows type of therapies given to CKD patients in GGH.

TABLE 4.8 TYPES OF THERAPIES

TYPES OF THERAPIES	NUMBER OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE
Mono therapy	12	16%
Dual therapy	49	43%
Triple therapy	59	33%
Multiple therapy	9	8%

FIG 4.8 TYPES OF THERAPIES**4.9 MONOTHERAPY OF ANTI- HYPERTENSIVES**

If only any one class of antihypertensives used then it is called Mono therapy. Most used class of the antihypertensives are calcium channel blockers with 47% followed by Angiotensin receptor blockers 26%, Diuretics 16%, Beta blockers 11%.

TABLE 4.9 MONOTHERAPY OF ANTI- HYPERTENSIVES

CLASS OF DRUGS	NUMBER OF PATIENTS
Calcium channel blockers	9
Diuretics	3
Angiotensin receptor blockers	5
Beta blockers	2

FIG 4.9 MONOTHERAPY OF ANTI- HYPERTENSIVES

4.10 DUAL THERAPY OF ANTI-HYPERTENSIVES

To improve morbidity of the patients more class of Anti hypertensives added Diuretic + Beta block (2.40%), Diuretic + Calcium channel blockers (17.34%) Diuretic + Angiotensin receptor blockers (12.24), Diuretic + Angiotensin converting enzyme inhibitors (2.40%), calcium channel blockers + Beta blockers (2.40%), Calcium channel blockers + Angiotensin receptor blockers (7.14%), calcium channel blockers + central sympatholytic (6.12%).

TABLE 4.10 DUAL THERAPY OF ANTI-HYPERTENSIVES

DUAL THERAPY	NUMBER OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE
Diuretic + Beta Blocker	2	2.40%
Diuretic + CCB	17	17.34%
Diuretic + ARBs	12	12.24%
CCB + Beta Blocker	2	2.40%
ARB + CCB	2	2.40%
Diuretic + ACE Inhibitor	2	2.40%
CCB + ARB	7	7.14%
CCB + Central Sympatholytic	6	6.12%

FIG 4.10 DUAL THERAPY OF ANTI-HYPERTENSIVES

4.11 TRIPLE THERAPY OF ANTI-HYPERTENSIVES

In this study to improve morbidity of the patients more class of Anti hypertensives added. Diuretics+ Calcium channel blockers + Beta blockers (58%), Diuretics + Central sympatholytic + Calcium channel blockers (16%), Diuretics + Angiotensin receptor blockers + Beta blockers (3%), Diuretics + Calcium channel blockers + Beta blockers (3%), Diuretics + Calcium channel blockers + Angiotensin receptor blockers (10%), Diuretics+ Nitrates+ Calcium channel blockers (3%), Diuretics + Calcium channel blockers + Nitrates (3%), Diuretics + Alpha+Beta blockers + Beta blockers (3%).

TABLE 4.11 TRIPLE THERAPY OF ANTI-HYPERTENSIVES

TRIPLE THERAPY	NUMBER OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE
Diuretics + CCB + Beta Blocker	22	58%
Diuretics + CS + CCB	7	16%
Diuretics + ARBs + Beta blocker	1	3%
Diuretics + CS + Beta Blocker	1	3%
Diuretics + CCB + ARB	4	10%
Diuretics + nitrates + CCB	2	6%
Diuretics + Alpha Blocker + Beta Blocker	1	3%

FIG 4.11 TRIPLE THERAPY OF ANTI-HYPERTENSIVES

4.12 MULTIPLE THERAPY OF ANTI-HYPERTENSIVES

Central sympatholytic + Calcium channel blockers + Beta blockers + Alpha+Beta blockers (12.5%), Diuretics + Beta blockers + Calcium channel blockers + Central sympatholytic (75%), Diuretics + Beta blockers+ Calcium channel blockers+ Nitrates (12.5%).

TABLE 4.12 MULTIPLE THERAPY OF ANTI-HYPERTENSIVES

MULTIPLE THERAPY	NUMBER OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE
Central sympatholytic + CCB +Beta Blocker + Alpha Blocker	1	12.50%
Diuretic + Beta Blocker + CCB+ Central sympatholytic	6	75%
Diuretic + Beta Blocker + CCB+ Nitrates	1	12.50%

FIG 4.12 MULTIPLE THERAPY OF ANTI-HYPERTENSIVES

5. DISCUSSION:

This study involved 120 CKD patients with hypertension to assess the prescription pattern of anti-hypertensive drugs. In our study, 58% males and 42% females were taken. In the present study most of the patients were given dual therapy (43%) followed by triple therapy (33%), this result is supported with the study by Ashok Kumar malapani et.al., that portrayed dual therapy in (78%) of prescription. Individuals with resistant hypertension will require more than or equal to three drugs out of which one is diuretic. Patients must be approached in a step wise manner beginning with traditional anti-hypertensive therapy followed by additional agents to reach a triple or quadruple or five drug compound regimens. Resistant hypertension is defined as blood pressure that remains above 140/90 mm Hg despite optimal use of three anti-hypertensive medications of different classes, including a diuretic. In the present study diuretics and calcium channel blockers are most preferred class of drugs that is used 31% each, which is supported with the study by Alwin P Saju et.al. Among monotherapy calcium channel blockers were most prescribed drug. In dual therapy Calcium channel blockers and Diuretics, in triple therapy diuretics, Calcium channel blockers, Beta blockers and in multiple therapy Diuretics, Beta blockers, Calcium channel blockers, Central sympatholytic are more frequently prescribed. Among Diuretics, furosemide is the most preferred drug, in Angiotensin receptor blockers, telmisartan. In Beta - blockers, metoprolol, in Alpha and Beta blockers, Labetalol, in Central sympatholytic, Clonidine and in Calcium channel blockers amlodipine f/b nifedipine and cilnidipine are more frequently prescribed.

6. CONCLUSION:

Our study concludes that males are more prone to Chronic kidney disease, Based on Age wise distribution 41-50 years, 51-60 years patients were hospitalized more frequently. Most of the patients were prescribed with Dual Therapy and Triple Therapy as most of the patients develops Resistant Hypertension. In Mono Therapy, Calcium channel blockers were more prescribed. Among all Anti-Hypertensives, Calcium channel blockers and Diuretics are most prescribed.

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